

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D9.8 Podcasts – Update M28

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Executive Summary

This deliverable builds upon the previous deliverable *D9.4 Podcast* and provides an update on the progress of the COVINFORM podcast. This deliverable describes our approach for developing the COVINFORM podcast, as one of the project's tools to disseminate and communicate the project results to our target audiences. Due to the nature of the medium, the general public and academia and scientific community were identified as the target audience for the podcast. Podcasts have been chosen as a means of one-way communication with the target audiences, given their potentially broad demographic reach and the gaining popularity of this format. In addition to the benefits of the podcasts, the nature of the medium enables the COVINFORM project to communicate key messages without having to radically simplify their meaning.

The title of the podcast series (*Beyond Numbers – COVID-19 pandemic & Society*) has been chosen to reflect COVINFORM's key messages. The framework of intersectionality was the main theme in most of the episodes, connecting various subjects the COVINFORM project encounters in its research. Each episode explored identified subjects related to the project and provided a detailed explanation of terminology, application of the theory in the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact on vulnerable groups.

The podcasts targeted a mixed audience, chosen based on the already established COVINFORM audience, the format of the medium and the podcast context. The mixed target audience consists of the general public and the scientific community. A total of five episodes were produced. The first episode of the podcast was launched at the end of January 2022 and the final episode is released at the end of February 2023.

The episode topics were carefully curated to reflect and amplify COVINFORM's areas of research. Overall, the scope of the themes not only comprehensively communicated COVINFORM's aims, but also established a thorough and accessible resource of information regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on society. The list of episodes can be seen below. Podcast episodes are accessible via podcast's public RSS feed - <https://rss.com/podcasts/beyondnumbers/>.

- Episode 1 - Intersectionality & Vulnerability
- Episode 2 - Communication & Public Health Campaigns
- Episode 3- Data, Interpretation & Misinformation
- Episode 4 – Gender, Mental Health and Migration
- Episode 5 - Community Voices – Bringing it all together

The podcast series is a task led by Trilateral Research as Work Package 9 (WP9) leader and podcast coordinator and is carried out in collaboration with all project partners.

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1 Introduction

The COVINFORM podcast is a demonstrator deliverable, which follows the deliverable *D9.2 Communication plan, D9.4 Podcast* and *D9.7 Communication Plan – Update M18*. Podcasts have been chosen as a means of one-way communication with the target audiences, given their potentially broad demographic reach and the gaining popularity of this format. In addition to the benefits of podcasts, the nature of the medium enables the COVINFORM project to communicate key messages without having to radically simplify their meaning.

This report provides an update of the podcast series, following from *D9.4 Podcast*. Firstly, this report outlines the concept of the podcasts, which has been formed together in a collaborative way among consortium members to reflect and amplify the main messages of the COVINFORM project, alongside other communication and dissemination activities (e.g. videos, bi-monthly reports, social media engagement etc.). To ensure the right target audiences are reached, this report establishes, based on the *D9.2 Communications plan* and *D9.7 Communication Plan – Update M18*, the selected target audiences for this particular means of communication. The report also outlines the timeframe in which the podcast episodes were produced, recorded and published. Lastly, the report encloses a detailed description of each episode, the rationale for each topic and the names of guest speakers appearing on each episode.

2 Podcast strategy

2.1 Concept

The concept of the podcasts has been discussed on multiple occasions with the project coordinator as well as with the consortium, who agreed that the key message of the podcasts should amplify the main takeaways of the COVINFORM project. Thus, the podcasts focus on the impact of COVID-19 on various intersecting vulnerabilities and the role of communication and governmental response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The title of the podcast series (*Beyond Numbers – COVID-19 pandemic & Society*) has been chosen to reflect the above-mentioned concept and key messages. The framework of intersectionality is the main theme in most of the episodes connecting various subjects the COVINFORM project encounters in its research. It is intended that each episode will look at each of the identified subjects and further provide a more detailed explanation of terminology, application of the theory in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact on vulnerable groups. The chosen topics and the rationale behind their selection is discussed more broadly in section 2.4 *Episode Topics* of this deliverable.

Update M28

The concept of the podcasts described above was maintained and reflected in all five podcast episodes. The focus of the COVINFORM podcast was to transmit key findings from the COVINFORM project, in an engaging and conversational manner. Each episode looked at a specific topic related to the COVINFORM project. More specifically, each episode provided an explanation of terminology and application of the theory in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact on vulnerable groups. Throughout the podcast episodes, the framework of intersectionality was the main theme and provided a common thread across episodes. Where relevant, links were made between podcast episodes to demonstrate connections between topics as well as highlight the holistic approach taken by the COVINFORM project.

2.2 Target Audiences

As far as the target audiences for the podcast are concerned, the consortium have agreed to cater to a mixed audience. On one hand, podcasts as a communication medium are gaining popularity amongst the general public, thus this specific target audience is one of the essential groups targeted. In *D9.2 Communications plan*, COVINFORM has established key messages relevant to different target audiences. In the case of the general public, the main message the COVINFORM project wants to convey is the understanding of various measures such as lockdowns, social isolation, mental and physical health etc. and their impact on society as a whole.

However, the COVINFORM podcast aims to communicate the main message from an intersectional point of view. Hence the second essential target audience is identified as the scientific community and academia. The COVINFORM project appeals to this particular target audience by contributing towards knowledge production within the fields of social sciences. Since the podcast will also discuss theoretical frameworks, which will be explained and applied to different topics, the scientific community and

academia are a direct target audience that could benefit from such material. Moreover, the podcast will communicate scientific insights and theoretical frameworks in an accessible and easy-to-understand way. Thus, it will be possible to raise the interest in the general population while still providing relevant scientific input to the scientific community. In addition, both chosen target audiences may be interested in receiving information on COVINFORM’s analysis of current responses and communication strategies employed by national planners and healthcare decision-makers.

Update M28

In *D9.2 Communications plan* and *D9.7 Communications plan – Update M18*, COVINFORM outlines its key messages and channels of communication in a way that guarantees that the different target audiences are provided with information relevant to them. In line with these deliverables and the description above, the COVINFORM podcast was aimed at the general public as well as academia and the scientific community.

2.3 Timeline

In order to keep the audience engaged, the podcast will come out on a periodic basis. The aim is to publish one episode per month, starting with the first episode published in January 2022. Consequently, the second episode will be published at the end of February, the third episode will be published at the end of March and so forth, for a total of five podcasts.

The regularly scheduled publishing date will not only help our audience to navigate the publishing schedule and manage their expectations relating to the podcasts’ frequency, but it will also aid the consortium when it comes to episode planning. To assure an attainable level of planning, each episode will be planned almost two months ahead of the publishing date. To date, episode two, which is planned for the end of February, has already been planned and the speakers confirmed.

Table 1 Example of episode planning & timeline showcased for Episode 2

Date	Task
10-21.1.2022	Meeting with COVINFORM guest speakers to go over the timeline & key messages
22.1.2022	Speakers confirmed
24.1.2022	Script first draft sent to the speakers & project coordinator
24.1.-2.2.2022	Revision period for the script
4.2.2022	Script finalised
7-11.2.2022	Episode 2 rehearsal
14-18.2.2022	Episode 2 recording
28.2.2022	Episode 2 release date

Update M28

As set out in the timeline above, the first episode of the COVINFORM podcast was published in January 2022. The following three podcast episodes were produced on a monthly basis, being published at the end of February, end of March and beginning of April 2022. The regular nature of the podcast episodes assured our audience were engaged with the content and the results presented from the COVINFORM project.

The fifth podcast episode was recorded in January 2023. The podcast episode was a commentary on a series of “stories” recorded by partners based on interviews conducted by the COVINFORM team with civil society organisations working with vulnerable groups during the pandemic (further detail in 2.5 Executive plan). Due to the more complex nature of the fifth podcast episode, involving the preparation and recording of “stories”, additional time was required to organise and record the podcast episode. The fifth podcast episode was released at the end of February 2023.

2.4 Episode topics

The COVINFORM podcast series is estimated to consist of five episodes covering various topics and themes encountered during the project. From a planning point of view, it has been decided to include two major themes within one episode. Nevertheless, it is essential that the two subjects are related and complement each other – either theoretically or practically. The topics have been identified from other material produced within the COVINFORM project, such as blogs, bi-monthly reports and whitepapers. In addition, the topics have been assessed during a Work Package (WP) 9 calls organised by Trilateral Research in November 2021. The partners had a chance to cooperate and brainstorm identified topics and suggest new ones. The collaborative process helped identify the most relevant topics, which have been selected and paired together.

Table 2 shows an overview of the planned episodes with the topic as well as the expected release date. Each episode topic description will be outlined in section 2.5 *Executive plan* of this deliverable.

Table 2 Podcast episode topics overview

Episode	Topic	Date published
Episode 1	Intersectionality & Vulnerability	30.1.2022
Episode 2	Communication & Public Health Campaigns	28.2.2022
Episode 3	Data, Memes & Misinformation	31.3.2022
Episode 4	Gender & Inequalities	30.4.2022
Episode 5	Government & Recommendations	31.5.2022

Update M28

The COVINFORM podcast series consisted of five episodes examining the main themes and outcomes of the project. The topics of the podcast episodes were discussed and decided jointly as a consortium during Work Package (WP) 9 calls organised by Trilateral Research. In the regular calls, the consortium assessed the upcoming podcast topics as well as provided feedback on the previously

produced podcast episodes. In comparison to the forecasted podcast episodes presented in Table 2, only a few changes were made to the podcast topics produced:

- Episode 3: incorporated the topic of interpretation of data instead of ‘memes’ to allow for a richer conversation on how data has been (mis)interpreted throughout the pandemic and the impact of this on vulnerable groups. Moreover, the addition of interpretation led nicely into the discussion around misinformation.
- Episode 4: in addition to discussing gender, the consortium agreed it would be useful to also converse about the topics of mental health and migration in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic, showcasing different aspects of the research conducted within the COVINFORM project.
- Episode 5: despite originally planning the fifth episode of the podcast to describe government approaches, public health and recommendations, the consortium agreed that the final episode of the podcast would instead draw from the interviews conducted with civil society organisations and reflect vulnerable groups’ experiences of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 3 Podcast episode topics overview – Update M28

Episode	Topic	Date published
Episode 1	Intersectionality & Vulnerability	28.1.2022
Episode 2	Communication & Public Health Campaigns	28.2.2022
Episode 3	Data, Interpretation & Misinformation	28.3.2022
Episode 4	Inequality - Gender, Mental Health & Migration	03.5.2022
Episode 5	Community Voices – Bringing it all together	24.02.2023

2.5 Executive plan

2.5.1 Episode 1 – Intersectionality & Vulnerability

The topic of the first episode has been chosen based on the importance of the two concepts for future episodes. It is fundamental that the frameworks of intersectionality and vulnerability are discussed and explained so the listener can grasp the implied message of the whole podcast series. The first episode also sets the scene and introduce the COVINFORM project, as it is going to be a frequent point of reference.

The episode starts with an introduction to the COVINFORM project, as mentioned above and it also introduces the speakers, Dr Viktoria Adler from SYNIO and Jil Molenaar from the University of Antwerp. The debate then moves to the background of intersectionality and vulnerability, touching upon Black feminism, the historical evolution of the theory on vulnerability and providing a general overview of the two concepts. The episode further offers exploration on how these two concepts come together in COVINFORM and complement each other.

In addition, the episode includes various examples of intersecting vulnerabilities. On the one hand, the aim is to focus on relatable and easily understandable examples from real-life situations, so the general public can better imagine and apply the theoretical concepts. On the other hand, the theory focused

content will be of benefit to the scientific community, as it promotes knowledge production in the field of social science drafted from the preliminary results of COVINFORM research and analysis.

Update M28

As outlined above, the first podcast episode provided an introduction to the podcast series as well as the COVINFORM project overall. The speakers were Dr Viktoria Adler (SYNYO) and Jil Molenaar (University of Antwerp). The discussion was based upon intersectionality theory, providing a definition and overview of the theory, as well as emphasising the relevance of intersectionality during the COVID-19 pandemic. The speakers then moved on to discussing the topic of vulnerability and how the two frameworks of intersectionality and vulnerability are brought together in the COVINFORM project.

2.5.2 Episode 2 - Communication & Public Health Campaigns

The second episode will focus on the topics of communication with a special segment on the public health campaigns. Communication is a concept tightly related to intersectionality and vulnerability; topics discussed in the first episode. The second episode will follow the discussion from episode one and enrich the concept of communication with the application to pandemic management.

According to the plan (see Table 1), the podcast guests are already confirmed at the time of submission of this deliverable. Partners participating in the production of the second episode are Dr Su Anson from Trilateral Research and Marva Arabatzi from KEMEA. The second episode will also include an external guest, Panagiotis Alefragis, who is the digital head of The Newtons Laboratory responsible for the production of public health campaigns in Greece.

As part of the episode, the COVINFORM experts will also introduce the concept of behaviour change and discuss elements of inclusive communication during a crisis, which is a part of COVINFORM WP7's focus. Furthermore, the preliminary results from COVINFORM research will be shared in the form of lessons learned. At the end of this episode, examples of public health campaigns will be communicated alongside Panagiotis' experience from producing such campaigns.

Update M28

The second episode focused on the topic of communication, with a segment of the episode dedicated to public health campaigns. The speakers were Dr Su Anson (TRI), Marva Arabatzi (KEMEA) and external guest Panagiotis Alefragis, digital head of The Newtons Laboratory in charge of the production of public health campaigns in Greece. The episode frequently looked back at the first episode that touched upon inclusive communication. The main themes discussed throughout the podcast were ensuring inclusive communication in times of crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the concept of behaviour change and public health campaigns.

2.5.3 Episode 3 – Data, Memes & Misinformation

Episode three will concentrate on no less important topic, which is data. On the one hand, during the pandemic, the general public has faced an unprecedented encounter with a great amount of data such

as the infection rates, but also more complicated statistical data for example from vaccine trials. On the other hand, the COVINFORM project is built on an interesting and innovative research methodology, which will be also a point of interest for the third episode. A partner from Trilateral Research, Niamh Aspell, will be responsible for explaining the methodology and research design in an accessible way, so the listeners (both the scientific community and the general public) can learn more about the COVINFORM project as well as how the data is leveraged in social science research. On top of that, topics such as memes and misinformation relating to COVID-19 will be touched upon, to establish examples of how important data science is.

Update M28

The third episode focused on the topic of data and statistics and the importance of interpretation of data during the COVID-19 pandemic. The speakers were Diotima Bertel (SYNYO), the COVINFORM project coordinator, and Dr Niamh Aspell (TRI). The main themes discussed throughout the episode were the importance of COVID-19 data reflecting vulnerable groups, and likewise, being accessible to vulnerable groups; as well as lessons learnt from the COVID-19 pandemic in relation to data collection and accessibility.

2.5.4 Episode 4 - Gender & Inequalities

The first episode has established a list of inequalities that have been either uncovered or deepened during the COVID-19 pandemic. The fourth episode will thus pay close attention to those inequalities and discuss them in more depth. The first and foremost inequality that will serve as an example of unequal systems will be gender. The debate will include many examples to establish the different impacts based on the chosen inequalities. Nevertheless, following the intersectional approach of the project, gender is not going to be the only addressed inequality. The guests will also discuss other inequalities such as disability, age, socioeconomic status or sexuality.

Update M28

The fourth episode focused on inequalities, more specifically the relationship between the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and gender, mental health and migration. The speakers were project partners Nuno Marques (FS) and Lore van Praag (UNANTWERPEN), and external speaker Sara Clavero, senior researcher on the EU-funded H2020 project RESISTIRÉ. The first topic of discussion was the gendered impact of COVID-19, highlighting why gender is considered an inequality and threats for future deepening of gendered inequality as a result of pandemic. The second topic of discussion was the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health and the role that inequality played in this impact. The final topic of discussion was the impact of COVID-19 on migrant communities and discrimination migrant communities faced during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as the increase in hate crimes and the discriminatory nature of some COVID-19 policies.

2.5.5 Episode 5 – Government & Recommendations (update M28 – Community voices: Bringing it all together)

The fifth and last episode of the COVINFORM podcast will be about governments, public health, communities and recommendations. Governments are considered the main coordinators of the response to the COVID-19 pandemic. They play an essential role when it comes to the effective management of the balance between the public health commitment and legal and ethical frameworks. The episode will discuss the findings of the research that the COVINFORM project conducted regarding governmental structures, social, economic, cultural, and legal factors that influenced specific governmental responses, communication measures and specific adaptations each country took towards specific vulnerable groups.

Update M28

The fifth podcast episode focused on the experiences of vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic as told by civil society organisations working closely with these groups. As mentioned in 2.4 *Podcast episodes*, the fifth episode had originally been planned to discuss government responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and specific adaptations made towards vulnerable groups' needs in different European countries. The consortium engaged in various discussions about the topic of the last episode and agreed that the fifth episode would focus on the findings from interviews conducted with civil society organisations (CSOs) to give voice to the experiences of vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic. Interesting extracts from the interviews were noted and transformed into "stories". These stories reflected cases of vulnerable groups and the impact that the COVID-19 had on these populations from the perspective of the civil society organisations that were supporting them. The stories were then recorded by the COVINFORM researchers.

The podcast episode consisted of a commentary and discussion based on these stories, reflecting on main insights to be drawn from them. The speakers were James Edwards (SINUS) and Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS). At the beginning of the episode, the term "community" is defined and MacQueen et al.'s (2001) theory of community is presented which identifies five core elements of community. Following this, the three "stories" were presented: the first on a CSO supporting migrant women in Austria; the second on a CSO working with a range of vulnerable groups in Spain and the third on a CSO supporting individuals with serious drug dependencies in Belgium. Speakers related the findings from the stories to the theory of community and pinpointed key good practices to supporting vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3 Podcast engagement

The podcast episodes have been published on the major streaming platforms RSS, Spotify and Apple Podcast. Since the launch of the COVINFORM podcast in January 2022, the podcast has been downloaded 858 times. The average downloads per episode are 215. As reflected in Figure 1, the first podcast episode has the highest number of downloads (N=294). The COVINFORM project will promote the fifth podcast episode once it is live on their website and social media channels and continue to promote the podcast as a whole.

Figure 1. Podcast engagement (N=downloads)

4 Conclusions

The report develops upon and provides an update on deliverable *D9.4. Podcast*. The COVINFORM podcast – *Beyond Numbers: COVID-19 pandemic & Society* – has been a communication medium with a potentially large demographic reach. The intersectionality was the critical lens through which the podcast examined, deconstructed and communicated themes analysed and researched in the COVINFORM project.

The podcast targeted a mixed audience consisting of the general public and the scientific community. The first episode of the podcast was released in January 2022 and the fifth and final episode of the podcast has been released in February 2023.

The collaborative process aided in choosing the episode topics, which have been carefully curated to reflect and amplify COVINFORM's areas of research. The episodes included topics such as Intersectionality, Communication, Data, Inequalities and Community Experiences. Overall, the scope of the themes not only comprehensively communicated COVINFORM's aims, but also established a thorough and accessible resource of information regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and society.

5 Podcast availability

The podcast episodes are available on the streaming platforms RSS, Apple Podcast and Spotify as well as on the COVINFORM website. Please find the link to podcast's RSS feed here: <https://rss.com/podcasts/beyondnumbers/>